

LABORATORY EVALUATION OF NEW ORGANIC PRODUCTS AGAINST *PLUTELLA XYLOSTELLA* LINNAEUS, *PIERIS BRASSICAE* AND *BREVICORYNE BRASSICAE* LINNAEUS IN CABBAGE

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ABSTRACT: Three replicated laboratory trials were carried out at the College of Agriculture, Imroisemba, CAU, Imphal during *Rabi* season of 2017 - 2018 to study the comparative bio-efficacy of four dosage (1, 2, 3 & 4 ml/lit.) of three new organic products *viz.*, Rodhak, Krimidote and Vridhak, and one neem formulation, Pestoneem (Azadirachtin 1500 ppm) @ 3 ml/lit. against the Diamond-backmoth, *Plutella xylostella* Linnaeus, the Cabbage butterfly, *Pieris brassicae* and the Cabbage aphid, *Brevicoryne brassicae* in cabbage variety "Pride of India". The results of laboratory evaluation of insecticides against these three insect pests revealed that all the insecticidal treatments were found significantly superior in reducing population of three pests as compared to untreated control. Krimidote @ 4 ml/lit was found to be most effective against *P.xylostella* and *P.brassicae* with mean larval population reduction of 84.64 and 84.65% followed by Krimidote @ 3 ml/lit (84.45 & 84.57%), Karimidote @ 2 ml/lit. (83.45 & 80.25%) and Karimidote @ 1 ml/lit. (82.35 & 878.85%), which did not differ significantly from each other and also was at par with Pestoneem (Azadirachtin 1500 ppm) @ 3 ml/lit. treatment (76.75 and 75.95%). While among the three products each at four dosage and Pestoneem at 3 ml/ml evaluated in reduction of *B. brevecoryne* population, Rodhak @ 4 ml/lit. was most effective treatment in reduction of aphid population with a record of mean per cent reduction of 89.77, but it was at par with Rodhak @ 3 ml/lit (87.23%), Rodhak @ 2 ml/lit (85.47%) and Rodhak @ 1 ml/lit (82.64%). The treatment with Vridhak @ 1 ml/lit proved least effective in suppression of the pests' population recording mean population reduction of 34.64 & 40.18% and 40.05%, respectively.

Key Words: *Plutella xylostella*, *Pieris brassicae*, *Brevicoryne brassicae*, cabbage

INTRODUCTION

In India, cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata* Linnaeus) is one of the most important cole crops grown throughout the country. It occupies an area of about 2,45,400 hectares with a production of 56,17,100 tonnes. However, the average productivity of cabbage in India is about 22,890 kg/ha, which is less than World's productivity of 23,985 kg/ha (FAO, 1999). In Manipur, the total area under cabbage is only 1,000 hectares with a production of 10,100 metric tonnes. The productivity is only 10,100 kg/ha in the State as compared to the national productivity of 22,890 kg/ha (ANON., 2002). Amongst several abiotic and biotic factors responsible for low productivity of cabbage, the damage caused by insect pests which infest the crop from seedling to harvest is considered as one of the major production constraints. Several broad-spectrum synthetic organic insecticides are usually recommended for the effective control of these pests (SONKAR and DESAI, 1999). However, these compounds are known to evoke multifarious problems including environmental pollution, health hazards, destruction of beneficial fauna like parasitic,

predatory and pollinating insects, resistance to insecticides, resurgence of secondary insect pests etc. Moreover, excessive use of such persistent insecticides on vegetables is acquiring a special concern since there is a little time lag between the last application and consumption. Owing to wide spectral problems with the use of these insecticides, use of bio-rational insecticides like organic products including Neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) commercial formulations is gaining popularity in Integrated Pest Management (IPM) because of their safety to non-targeted organisms and non-biomagnification in the food chain and easily biodegradable. These products are more compatible (ISMAN, 1994) with the environmental components, eco-friendly with plant health and non-hazardous to human beings (ARNASON *et al.*, 1989). We conducted research to test the effectiveness of 3 organic products against 3 most major insect pests *viz.*, Diamond back-moth, *Plutella xylostella* Linn.; cabbage butterfly, *Pieris brassicae* Linn. & cabbage aphid, *Brevicoryne brassicae* Linn. using cabbage variety "Pride of India".

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The laboratory studies were conducted in the Department of Entomology, College of Agriculture, Central Agricultural University, Imphal to investigate the comparative bio-efficacy of four dosage each of three organic insecticides *viz.*, Rodhak, Krimidote and Vridhak, and one neem formulation (Pestoneem) against the diamond back moth, *Plutella xylostella* Linnaeus, the cabbage butterfly, *Pieris brassicae* Linnaeus and the cabbage aphid, *Brevicoryne brassicae* Linnaeus using cabbage var. "Pride of India" during Rabi, 2017 and 2018. The methodology used and adopted is briefly stated below:

A. Rearing of insects as a stock culture: For rearing of insects in the laboratory, petridishes of 150 mm x 25mm size were used. About 200 each insect populations were collected from the field where no synthetic organic and other chemical insecticides was applied and kept in petridishes for multiplication. The fresh cabbage leaves of test variety were provided as food regularly to the insects.

B. Treatment details

Treatment	Insecticide	Dose
T ₁	Rodhak	@ 1 ml/lit. of water
T ₂	Rodhak	@ 2 ml/lit. of water
T ₃	Rodhak	@ 3 ml/lit. of water
T ₄	Rodhak	@ 4 ml/lit. of water
T ₅	Krimidote	@ 1 ml/lit. of water
T ₆	Krimidote	@ 2 ml/lit. of water
T ₇	Krimidote	@ 3 ml/lit. of water
T ₈	Krimidote	@ 4 ml/lit. of water
T ₉	Vridhak	@ 1 ml/lit. of water
T ₁₀	Vridhak	@ 2 ml/lit. of water
T ₁₁	Vridhak	@ 3 ml/lit. of water
T ₁₂	Vridhak	@ 4 ml/lit. of water
T ₁₃	Pestoneem (Azadirachtin 1500 ppm)	@ 3 ml/lit. of water
T ₀	Control	Water

Details of the organic products

(i) **RODHAK** (product formulated based on ingredients like Chamomile herb, *Athemis nobilis*; Custard apple; *Jatropha curcas*; Black pepper; Karanj oil; Neem oil and Molasses);

(ii) **KRIMIDOTE** (product formulated based on ingredients like Arduzi, *Solanum xati*, Lemo grass, Garlic, Neem oil, Karanj oil, Devadar oil and Tulasi);

(iii) **VRIDHAK** (product formulated based on ingredients like Ashwagadha, *Withania somnifera*; Chitrak, *Plumbago zeylanica*; *Aloe vera*; Seaweed and Citric acid).

C. Details of the experiment

Laboratory evaluation of four dosage (1, 2, 3 & 4 ml/lit.) each of three new organic products viz., Rodhak, Krimidote and Vridhak, and one Neem formulation Pestoneem (Azadirachtin 1500 ppm) @ 3 ml/lit. against the Diamond backmoth, *P.xylostella*, the Cabbage butterfly, *P. brassicae* and the Cabbage aphid, *B. brassicae* in cabbage variety "Pride of India" was made. There were fourteen treatments including one control, each treatment was replicated four times. The fresh leaves of cabbage var. "Pride of India" were obtained from the chemical insecticides unsprayed field and washed thoroughly with tap water. Each leaf was dipped into an insecticides solution and then dried under ceiling fan in a petriplates (150 mm X 25 mm size). A control with water was run simultaneously. Twenty healthy larvae (for *P. brassicae* & *P. xylostella*) and aphids collected from the laboratory rearing cages and conditioned for 24 hours, then released into each petriplate containing treated leaves. The insect population was counted after 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 days of the release. There were altogether 14 (fourteen) treatments including one control which each replicated thrice. The percentage population reduction was computed by using following formula:

$$\% \text{ reduction} = \frac{\text{No. of insect released} - \text{No. of surviving insect after treatment}}{\text{Number of insect released}} \times 100$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Laboratory comparative efficacy of four dosage of three new organic products against *Plutella xylostella* Linnaeus, *Pieris brassicae* Linnaeus and *Brevicoryne brassicae* Linnaeus on cabbage var. "Pride of India"

a) Effect of insecticides on larval population of *P. xylostella*

It was revealed from Table 1 & Fig. 1 that all the insecticidal treatments exhibited significantly reduction of larval population over control. However, Krimidote @ 4 ml/lit. was found to be the most effective with mean per cent reduction of 84.64 as against 4.65% reduction in untreated control. It was at par with Krimidote @ 3 ml/lit. (84.45%), Krimidote @ 2 ml/lit. (83.45%) and Krimidote @ 1 ml/lit. (82.35%). The treatments with Rodhak@ 4 ml/lit and Pestoneem @ 3 ml/lit were also exhibited moderately effective against *P. xylostella* with a record of higher mean population reduction of 79.67 and 76.75%, respectively which showed non significant difference between them. The Vridhak @ 1 ml/lit. treatment was the least effective treatment in reducing larval population of *P. xylostella* with a record of minimum mean per cent reduction of 34.64. KLEMM and SCHMUTTERER (2000) reported from the results of a field study conducted in Taiwan that neem (*Azadirachta indica*) seed kernal extracts (25 or 30 g seed kernal/litre of water) significantly reduced the number of larval population of *P. xylostella* which encouraged the present findings obtained for Pestoneem. The reports of SAUCKE *et al.* (2000) are also supporting the preset results of Pestoneem, who made a field study on evaluation of a few eco-friendly insecticides against *P. xylostella*, commercial neem formulations neemazal (*A. indica*) and an aqueous neem seed kernel extract from seeds were found to be superior to *B. thuringiensis* products (Delfin

& Thuricide) & synthetic insect growth regulator chlorfluazuron (Atabion).

b) Effect of insecticides on larval population of *P. brassicae*

All the insecticidal treatments proved to be significantly superior over control in reducing larval population of *P. brassicae* (Table 1 & Fig. 1). Krimidote @ 4 ml/lit. offered the best control of the pest which exhibited maximum mean larval population (84.65%) as against 3.95% in untreated control. It was closely followed by Krimidote @ 3 ml/lit. (84.57%), Krimidote @ 2 ml/lit. (80.25%), Krimidote @ 1 ml/lit. (78.85%), Pestoneem @ 3 ml/lit. (75.95%) and Rodhak @ 4 ml/lit. (72.33%) which exhibited non significant difference from one another. Minimum mean per cent larval population reduction (40.18%) was recorded from the treatment with Vridhak @ 4 ml/lit. The mean larval population reduction recorded in the treatment with Vridhak @ 4 ml/lit. was at par with that of Vridhak @ 3ml/lit. (41.25%), Vridhak @ 2 ml/lit. (40.68%) and Vridhak @ 1 ml/lit. (40.18%). The results on moderate efficacy of Neem formulation Pestoneem@ 3 ml/lit. against *P. brassicae* are in agreement with the reports of JACOBSON (1987); MORDUE (2004); PAVELA *et al.*, (2004), JAYASANKAR *et al.* (2005) and SINGH *et al.* (2012) who reported the treatment with Neem EC (1% Azadirachtin) was found to be the most effective one against *P. brassicae*. The effectiveness of Pestoneem might be due to contain of Azadirachtin and other Neem plant tetranortriterpenoids compounds responsible for antifeedant and repellent action which caused a delay in the feeding of *P. brassicae* larvae.

c) Effect of insecticides on larval population of *B. brassicae*

The mean percentage aphid population reduction based on two experimental years of seven time intervals under observation data of insecticides against *B. brassicae* presented in Table 1 and illustrated in Fig. 1 revealed that all the insecticidal treatments proved to be significantly superior to the untreated control in reducing the aphid population. However, Rodhak @ 4 ml/lit demonstrated its superiority in population reduction with 89.77% mortality closely followed Rodhak @ 3 ml/lit., Rodhak @ 2 ml/lit. and Rodhak @ 1 ml/lit with their corresponding mean population reduction of 87.23, 85.47 and 82.64%, respectively which exhibited insignificant difference between them. The mean aphid mortality recorded in rest of the insecticidal treatments varied from 40.05 to 79.45% which minimum being recorded in Vridhak @ 1 ml/lit and maximum in Pestoneem @ 3 ml/lit treatments. The untreated control treatment recorded the mean mortality of 4.15%.

The results on moderate efficacy of neem formulation Pestoneem@ 3 ml/lit against *B. brassicae* are in partial agreement with the reports of MORDUE (2004); PAVELA *et al.*, (2004), JAYASANKAR *et al.* (2005) and SINGH *et al.* (2012) who observed the more efficacy of Neem formulation against *B. brassicae*. The effectiveness Pestoneem might be due to contain of Azadirachtin and other Neem plant tetranortriterpenoids compounds responsible for antifeedant and repellent action on these three pests of Cabbage. However, The authors did not come across any related literature to discuss with the present results on the most effectiveness of Krimidote @ 4 ml/lit. against *P. xylostella* and *P. brassicae*, and Rodhak @ 4 ml/lit. against *B. brassicae*.

Table-1: Relative effect of insecticides on the population of *P. xylostella*, *P. brassicae* and *B. brassicae* in cabbage 'Pride of India' during Rabi, 2017 and 2018

Treatment	Dose in one litre of water	¹ Mean per cent population reduction after treatment based on two experimental seasons of 2017 and 2018		
		<i>P. xylostella</i>	<i>P. brassicae</i>	<i>B. brassicae</i>
Rodhak	1 ml	41.56(39.28)	41.25(35.21)	82.64(78.21)
Rodhak	2 ml	41.85(39.28)	42.75(37.64)	85.47(73.55)
Rodhak	3 ml	73.65(64.15)	44.12(69.85)	87.23(75.68)
Rodhak	4 ml	79.67(72.65)	72.33(64.27)	89.77(79.25)
Krimidote	1 ml	82.35(73.30)	78.85(71.44)	44.25(38.56)
Krimidote	2 ml	83.45(74.15)	80.25(76.25)	45.35(38.55)
Krimidote	3 ml	84.45(74.45)	84.57(77.74)	76.33(68.21)
Krimidote	4 ml	84.64(78.25)	84.65(76.61)	76.52(61.86)
Vridhak	1 ml	34.64(30.95)	40.18(35.35)	40.05(32.26)
Vridhak	2 ml	36.43(34.15)	40.68(36.35)	40.25(31.45)
Vridhak	3 ml	37.05(32.26)	41.25(35.21)	43.26(34.23)
Vridhak	4 ml	40.66(37.48)	42.75(37.64)	43.74(38.52)
Pestoneem (Azadirachtin 1500 ppm)	3 ml	76.75(69.85)	75.95(69.85)	79.45(65.79)
Control	Water	4.65(3.91)	3.95(2.86)	4.15(3.24)
CD(P=0.05)	-	12.12	15.65	4.89

Figures in parentheses are angular transformed values;

¹Mean of seven observations recorded at 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7 days after treatment based on four replications.

Fig. 1: Graphical representation on effect of organic products on population reduction (%) of the pests

CONCLUSION: The significant results generated from the present study on laboratory evaluation of four dosage each of three organic insecticides viz., Rodhak, Krimidote and Vridhak, and one neem formulation (Pestoneem) against the diamond back moth, *Plutella xylostella* Linnaeus, the cabbage butterfly, *Pieris brassicae* Linnaeus and the cabbage aphid, *Brevicoryne brassicae* Linnaeus carried out during Rabi, 2017 and 2018 in the Department of Entomology, College of Agriculture, Iroisemba, Central Agricultural University, Imphal leads to conclusion that need based application of Krimidote @ 3-4 ml/lit. for *P. xylostella* & *P. brassicae* and Rodhak @ 3-4 ml/lit. for *B. brassicae* can be done to manage these pests in order to produce the good quality cabbage vegetable.

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